

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT ON ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIORS

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Abstract. Organisation of its practical importance and implications for businesses, organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) has gotten a lot of attention from researchers recently. The goal of this study was to look at the relationship between secondary school teachers' job attitudes and organisational citizenship behaviour. To achieve the goals, a cross-sectional design was employed. A questionnaire was given to 250 secondary school teachers in Perak, and data was collected. We had an 80% response rate. The respondents answered questions about job satisfaction, commitment, and organisational citizenship behaviour on a questionnaire. A convenience sample method was used to pick the respondents. Because of its practical importance and implications for businesses, organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) has gotten a lot of attention from researchers recently. The goal of this study was to look at the relationship between secondary school teachers' job attitudes and organisational citizenship behaviour. The design was cross-sectional. The chi-square and T-tests were used to assess the data. Job satisfaction, organisational commitment, and organisational citizenship conduct all showed statistically significant and favourable correlations, according to the findings.

KEYWORDS: Chi-Square Test, T-Test, Organisational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB), Job Satisfaction.

1. Introduction

[1]Managers who feel that "An company has a responsibility to provide employees with challenging and intrinsically satisfying employment" value high employee satisfaction. (According to Robbins). Job satisfaction, according to Golbasi, is an emotional reaction and behavioural expression to a job that stems from an individual's judgement of his or her work achievement, office environment, and work life. Employment satisfaction, according to Lock is "the pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job as accomplishing or enabling one's job values." Job satisfaction has an indirect impact on turnover, according to Price and Mueller, because it has a direct impact on the forming of intent to leave. Organ published a review of the theory in 1977. [19] The logic behind the satisfaction-performance relationship, which is linked to social exchange theory, in which performance is seen as an appropriate form of transaction to the firm in exchange for an employee's job satisfaction (Organ). As a result, those who are more satisfied with their jobs exhibit more pro-social, OCB behaviours (Bateman and Organ). [1]According to Kim, employees who have a higher level of job satisfaction have a higher level of OCB. According to this logic, job happiness should have a positive

association with teachers' citizenship behaviour, and the following hypothesis is proposed.

2. Attitudes on the job and corporate citizenship

[19] Organizational commitment is developed when the employee and the organisation develop a higher interest in preserving their working relationship, according to Meyer and Allen and Davenport. Employees that are emotionally linked to their employers have been proven to engage in more civic behaviour in previous studies (Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch, and Topolnytsky). This link is especially clear in the case of affective commitment (Meyer and Allen [3]). Organizational commitment, according to Meyer and Allen, is made up of three elements: affective, continuation, and normative commitment. Affective commitment, according to the authors, is described as "the employee's emotional attachment to, identification with, and involvement in the organisation." There is more evidence for a substantial association between commitment and OCB based on Becker's findings. According to Truckenbrodt, there is a considerable link.

Table of observed values

Qualification\ Marital status	Middle School	High School	Bachelor's	Master's	Ph.D	Total
Never married	18	36	21	9	6	90
Married	12	36	45	36	21	150
Divorced	6	9	9	3	3	30
Widowed	3	9	9	6	3	30
Total	39	90	84	54	33	300

Table of Expected Values

Qualification\ Marital status	Middle School	High School	Bachelor's	Master's	Ph.D
Never married	11.5	27	25.2	16.2	9.9
Married	19.5	45	42	27	16.5
Divorced	3.9	9	8.4	5.4	3.3
Widowed	3.9	9	8.4	5.4	3.3

3. Chi-Square

A chi-square goodness of fit test determines if sample data matches a population. A chi-square test for independence compares two variables in a contingency table to see if they are related. In a more general sense, it tests to see whether distributions of categorical variables differ from each other [10].

3.1 Chi Square Test:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{E_i}$$

χ^2 = chi squared

O_i = observed value

E_i = expected value

Degrees of freedom = (columns-1)(rows-1)

= (5-1) (4-1)

= 4×3

=12

Significance level (α) = 0.05

$$\chi_{tabulator}^2 = 21.03$$

$$\chi_{calculator}^2 = 23.57$$

We reject Null hypothesis and accept alternate hypothesis.

3.2 T-test:

[10]A t-test is a type of inferential statistic used to determine if there is a significant difference between the means of two groups, which may be related in certain features. It is mostly used when the data sets, like the data set recorded as the outcome from flipping a coin 100 times, would follow a normal distribution and may have unknown variances.

3.3 T-test:

$$t = \frac{|\bar{x} - \mu|}{S} \times \sqrt{n}$$

t = employee t-test

s = Standard derivation

n = variable set size

$$S = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(X - \bar{X})^2}{n - 1}}$$

X = 18,12,6,3,39

$\mu = 3$

—

$\bar{X} = 15.6, n = 5$

S = 12.5786

T = 1.7066

4. Techniques

4.1 Sample and procedure:

The survey was distributed to various secondary schools in Perak, Malaysia. [2] Data for this study were gathered using a self-administered written questionnaire. Invitation letters and questionnaire packs were sent to the principals of the selected secondary schools, who were asked to distribute the questionnaires to the teachers [4]. The questionnaire packs took about 15 minutes to complete and included measures of Job Attitude such as Job Satisfaction, Commitment, and Organizational Citizenship Behavior, as well as demographic information about the teachers.

4.2 Measures:

The survey questionnaire items were based on Paul E. Spector's Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS), an instrument developed for the comprehensive assessment of job satisfaction. Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) is a 36-item questionnaire that assesses nine aspects of a job [5]. "I owe a great deal to my organisation." and "This organisation has a great deal of personal value for me." The questionnaire was divided into three sections:[10] The demographic questions are found in Section A. Section B has work satisfaction questions, Section C contains commitment questions, and Section D contains organisational citizenship behaviour questions.

5. Analyzing data

The frequency, mean score, and standard deviations of demographic data, job satisfaction, commitment, and organisational citizenship behaviour were reported using descriptive statistics. Pearson's correlation and regression analysis were used to

analyse the association between work satisfaction, commitment, and organisational citizenship behavior[12].

The findings of this study suggest that the association between job attitudes and commitment warrants further investigation. Its generalizability is directly hampered by the convenience sample. More study using a similar approach, larger samples, and in different contexts would yield useful results [14].

6. Conclusion

The current study indicated that both job satisfaction and organisational commitment were positive. Future research in this field is likely necessary, given the practical and theoretical. Given the importance of teachers in today's education of young minds, it is hoped that the findings of this study would assist school administrators in gaining a better understanding of teachers' job attitudes and their impact on organisational civic behaviour.

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